

Current balance	178,771	How do you see the expansion?	It is a process to allow an organization to focus resources on the greatest opportunities to increase sales and achieve the company's target. Marketing strategy's goal is to increase sales and achieve the advantage over other competitors. It involves short-term and long-term activities of marketing that help to do with the analysis of a company's situation and contribute to its expansion. The objectives will be based on how you gain sales by acquiring and keeping customers.
Large Bank Accounts	844,179	What are your customers?	Marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets etc.
Investment Accounts	117,143	What are your customers?	Marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets etc.
Current Account	447,271	What are your customers?	Marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets etc.
Debit Cards	10,700	What are your customers?	Marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets etc.
Card - Credit Card	678,000	What are your customers?	Marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets etc.
Resources	4,567,004	What are your customers?	Marketing strategy helps in making good messages with the right kind of marketing approaches in order to have a good view of your sales and marketing activities. Putting your strategy into action is how your plan should work. Marketing budgets will be set, at the same time it will also show you you're going to work with your targets etc.

Market Strategy

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THE DAILY

FAKE NEWS

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ECONOMY OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

WORLD BANK'S STOCK AT ALL-TIME HIGH / US RATE RISE CHANCES RECEDE AS JOBS GROWTH SLOW

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Political parties and the state in Romania:

between dependence on state resources and its capture

Cristina Matiuta⁷

Abstract

Starting from party literature in the post-communist context, the paper aims to analyze several dimensions of party-state linkage in Romania:

1. the dependence of political parties on public subsidies and impact of regulation;
2. the share of public subsidies in the total budget of political parties by examining their revenues collected in recent years and their financial behavior;

3. the practices of embezzling public money and using state resources for electoral purposes, by referring to several corruption scandals related to their funding. It suggests that, as laws became clearer and more restrictive, the methods of those engaged in corrupt practices seem to be refined as well and that a more generous financing of political parties does not automatically entail a greater integrity of their behavior and practices.

Keywords: Party-state relationship, Subsidies, Donations, Embezzlement, Clientelism

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1. Introduction

Political parties are traditionally analyzed in societal terms; therefore, an extensive body of literature on their birth and evolution in the post-communist context refers to their position within society.

Many comparative studies emphasize the weak social roots of post-communist parties, taking into account a variety of indicators, such as high levels of electoral volatility, low levels of party identification/party membership or declining voter turnout to find out their feeble anchoring into society (Rose and Mishler, 1998; De Waele, 2002; Gherghina, 2011; Van Biezean, 2013; Matiuta, 2018).

But while political parties' connection with citizens is rather weak and unstable, things are different when we look at their relationship with the state in the post-communist context. Many scholars argue that since the very beginning of democratization process political parties have strongly penetrated the state (Van Biezen, 2007; Grzymała-Busse, 2007; Smilov & Toplak, 2007; Roper & Istkens, 2008, Kopecký, 2008, Mungiu-Pippidi, 2010) and these strong links with the state are both a consequence and a cause of their thin presence on the ground: "It is a consequence because parties need the state for material resources in the absence of strong roots in the wider society, and it is a cause because, once in possession of state resources, parties are significantly less compelled to engage in party-building strategies based on popular mobilization and extensive organizational development" (Kopecký, 2008, p. 3).

The party-state linkages since the early phases of post-communist transition involve areas that have been widely discussed in the literature, from party regulation by the laws of the state and their dependence on public subsidies, to the degree to which parties themselves colonize the state through rent-seeking behavior such as patronage and clientelism. Starting from the literature on party-state relationship in the new democracies, this paper examines the state embezzlement practices in Romania, a country affected by multiple corruption scandals in the post-communist decades, where citizens have little confidence in institutions and politicians. Although a single case study, the analysis could have an explanatory power for a broader area and may be relevant and for other countries as well, by identifying the changing patterns of state embezzlement once the legislation has become clearer and more severe.

Source: [freepik.com](https://www.freepik.com).

Photo by [wavebreakmedia_micro](https://www.wavebreakmedia.com).

This article focuses on the last post-communist decade (2011-2021), marked by a considerable increase in the financing of political parties by the state, mapping the changes in both the party finances of Romanian parties and the legislation regulating them. Thus, **the main questions that this study seeks to answer are whether increasing the funding of political parties and increasing the severity of legislation in the field have led to increased integrity of the political process, diminishing clientelist practices and illegal practices.**

To answer these questions, the paper examines three categories of evidence:

1. Regulation, with the latest amendments, to find out on what criteria are party funds allocated and whether the legislation creates leverage to ensure transparency of financing and the fairness of electoral competitions.

2. Funding and expenses of political parties. I track the revenues collected by them in the recent years, from members' contributions, donations and public subsidies in order to have a picture of the main contributors to the parties' budgets. The article seeks to find out who are the main contributors to party budgets, what is the share of public subsidies in the total party budgets, and how the money is spent.

3. Documented cases of malpractice (fraud and corruption) in relation with party finance. The article refers to some illustrative cases of corruption in the attempt to unravel mechanisms of public money fraud. The list of case presented is by no means exhaustive, but it tries to capture the most widely used methods of directing public money into campaign coffers or politicians' pockets.

The research draws on qualitative content analysis of PCF (party & campaign finance) legislation, media reports and reports published by the Permanent Electoral Authority, the state institution with competences in electoral matters. All the data about the incomes and expenses of the political parties are official data, published by the Permanent Electoral Authority. As regards specific cases considered relevant for deciphering the mechanisms of embezzlement of the state, the paper makes references to news agencies and press articles covering those cases.

The article is organized as follows. It begins with a review of the literature on patronage, clientelism and party funding in the former communist countries, particularly in Romania. The next section makes a brief presentation of the Romanian party system and the regulations regarding their financing. Then it analyzes the income sources of the political parties in the last decade, the way the money is spent and, using some examples, tries to highlight the mechanisms of embezzlement of the state through illegal/abusive use of public money. The last part of the paper summarizes the main findings and possible recommendations.

2. Theoretical framework: dimensions of party-state linkage in post-communist Europe

There is a rich literature dealing with different dimensions and facets of the relationship between political parties and the state in the former communist countries of Central and Eastern Europe.

Petr Kopecký explores three forms of this relationship: 1). the extent to which parties depend on the state, expressed by public funding of parties, free access to the media, tax exemptions, as a means of subsidizing (or even surviving) political parties; 2). the extent to which the parties are managed by the state, referring to the involvement of the state in the internal affairs of the parties by regulating their organization, activities and financing; and 3). the extent to which parties colonize the state, expressed by the seizure of the state apparatus through patronage, clientelism and corruption (Kopecký, 2008, p. 5). Party patronage involves the allocation of jobs and positions in the public sector, in state-owned companies, boards of directors, even in schools, universities and research institutes. Access to state resources provides party leaders the means to build and then maintain party organizations by distributing “selective incentives” to party activists and elites in exchange for their loyalty. Patronage thus becomes, to a certain extent, a resource for anchoring parties in the political system, which compensates the poorly developed organizational networks and the lack of strong ties within society.

Closely related to patronage, clientelism is an even more penetrating phenomenon, remarks Kopecký; it involves the selective transfer of various parts of public material resources (contracts, subsidies, housing, sponsorships, etc.) to individuals or certain segments of society, for ensuring electoral support. While in the prosperous democracies the areas and the size of the public sector (and therefore the resources that parties could distribute to potential clients) have steadily decreased, as well as the number of paupers (voting in exchange for material benefits), in the former communist states, or at least in some of them, the demand for such benefits is high especially within the poor rural communities.

When analyzing the relationship between political parties and the state, many studies emphasize the institutional legacies of the communist regime and the variations in the levels of patronage and clientelism practices between the former communist states (Gherghina and Volintiru, 2020; Kopecký and Spirova, 2011; Volintiru, 2015). The scholars argue that “is better to speak about a plurality of communist regimes” (rather than the communist regime generally), because their administrative structures and institutional arrangements were not the same, hence deriving different patterns of patronage politics in the post-communist period, seeing that long-established political routines and practices have not disappeared with the communism’s end (Kopecký and Spirova, 2011, p. 900).

In a comparative analysis of party appointments within the state institutions in three post-communist countries- Bulgaria, Czech Republic and Hungary- Petr Kopecký and Maria Spirova observe variations in the levels of patronage which are driven by the legacy of the communist regime. Thus, there is “more extensive patronage in the Bulgarian political system and its legacy of paternalistic communist regime than in the Czech case where the bureaucracy has been seen as more powerful prior to 1989” (Kopecký and Spirova, 2011, p. 911). As far as Romania is concerned, the studies reveal that patronage and clientelism exert a strong influence in the public administration at both central and local levels, political interference being an important factor in civil servants recruitment and promotion, even if the law protects them of political encroachment.

As Steven D. Roper remarks, “laws are not enough to provide accountability” (Roper, 2006). His study dealing with the influence of party patronage and state finance on electoral outcomes in the first two post-communist decades in Romania, shows that the awarding of patronage and use of party & campaign finance (PCF) do not always guarantee the electoral success. The author gives the example of the Social Democratic Party that used the state patronage and enjoyed considerable PCF throughout the 2000s, but these resources did not prevent the party to be removed from power following the 2004 national elections.

In a comparative assessment of four Central and East European countries- Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, and Romania-, based on a methodology developed by Kopecký, Mair, and Spirova (2012), Clara Volintiru finds that Romania has one of the highest scores of party patronage in the European Union, the economic, media and healthcare sectors being the most heavily politicized.

The patronage is an instrument of Romanian political parties for preferential and politicized appointments in public institutions: “Through political patronage, different employment and appointment procedures are manipulated to best fit the interests of the political patron – be it a party organisation or a party leader. In this sense, it is the most important form of politicisation: through the appointment of political clients in key positions of the state apparatus, parties or political patrons can manipulate other forms of state resources, that is, channel funds or discretionarily manage state assets” (Volintiru, 2015, p. 41). Looking into the mechanisms that link ruling parties to public appointments, this study emphasizes how, with every political turnover, the winning party/parties fills the positions in the public administration with party members or supporters, this “cleaning up” process (as is commonly named) touching the various levels of public sector (even if civil servants are not political functions and as such should not be directly affected by the electoral cycles). The result is an erosion of Romanian institutions, caused both by the high incidence of patronage and clientelism and by the way such practices are perceived to be the norm.

A thorough research about clientelism and state exploitation by political parties in Romania examines four main categories of spoil: public jobs (the public sector being extremely politicized, ruling parties filling with their own people not only the political jobs but many civil servant offices as well); public spending (such as procurement, subsidies, loans from state banks etc.); preferential concessions and privatizations from former state property; and market advantages in the form of preferential regulation (Ionita, Nutu, Stefan and Mungiu-Pippidi, 2011, p.8). The study focuses on several indicators to capture the mechanisms and dimension of the corrupt practices in the key public sectors, finding that “preferential allocation of funds and government favoritism are systemic and practiced openly”.

Other research also highlights the clientelistic spending of public money in Romania: “The top winners of public contracts are top donors to government parties’ electoral campaigns funds” (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2010, p.6), the discretionary allocation of public funds being a persistent problem during the country’s transition to democracy. One of the most used instruments in this regard is the so-called State Reserve Fund, established since 2002 by the Public Finance Law for natural disasters and unexpected situations. A study investigating its use over 2004-2012 electoral cycles shows how this fund is increased discretionarily through government decisions and distributed on grounds of political affiliation. The most money goes, as an unwritten rule, to the ruling parties and their own mayors at local level and not necessarily for real natural emergencies (Dimulescu, Pop and Doroftei, 2013, p. 86-87).

As an important dimension of party-state linkage, the party regulation and their funding in the post-communist democracies of Central and Eastern Europe received the scholarly attention as well.

The creation of the institutional context within which political parties operate, of legal regulations for an increased control on the origin of party funds and their spending are fundamental for the proper running of democracy (Roper and Ikstens, 2008). Studies on the financing of political parties highlight the relevance of public funding for party survival in an independent format in the system. Based on a comparison of 14 post-communist party systems, Casal Bertoa and Spirova show that the survival rate for parties receiving state funding exceeds the survival rate for the non-publicly funded ones and that parties outside parliaments but above the payout threshold display higher survival rates than parties that are below it (Casal Bertoa and Spirova, 2019).

At the same time, the widespread availability of the state support in the new democracies of Central and Eastern Europe has led to the financial dependence of political parties on the state “that is generally quite staggering, with estimates for share of public subsidies to the total party income varying from 60% to 85%” and “although important improvements to the rules have been made since the early 1990s the regulation of party finance has not been able to diminish the increasing levels of both party patronage and/or corruption in the region” (Casal Bertoa and Van Biezen, 2014, p. 305). In a study covering the evolution of party and campaign finance regulations in the first two post-communist decades in Romania, Sergiu Gherghina and Mihai Chiru highlight that once stricter regulations were introduced, political parties have found ways to avoid them and to get access to additional funds. Using examples of practices employed by political parties in 2000, 2004 and 2008 parliamentary elections, the paper illustrates how political parties abused public money through indirect channels such as generous public contracts awarded to donor companies. “The laws on party funding could not cover the entire spectrum of tricks political parties have devised to abuse state resources” conclude the authors (Gherghina and Chiru, 2013, p. 11).

Following such approaches, this paper aims to find out whether these corrupt practices, recurring during the post-communist years, are diminished by the improvements brought to the PCF legislation meant to increase funding transparency and control of the origin of the funds and by a more generous financing of the parties from the state budget in recent years. The following section provides a brief description of the Romanian party system and of the legal framework of party & campaign funding.

3. The Romanian party system: old and new parties and the regulation of their funding

In its current form, the Romanian party system includes five main competitors, namely three old parties (PSD-The Social Democratic Party; PNL- The National Liberal Party; UDMR-The Democratic Union of Hungarians in Romania), with a constant presence in parliament since 1990, and two new parties (USR-PLUS and AUR- The Alliance for the Union of Romanians), established in recent years.

The Social Democratic Party (PSD) has enjoyed the largest electoral support in the post-communist elections. Considered the main successor of the Communist Party, PSD (which has had several names over time: The National Salvation Front-FSN, between 1990-1992; The Democratic National Salvation Front-FDSN, between 1992-1993; The Party of Social Democracy in Romania- PDSR, between 1993-2001; and PSD since 2001) won the most votes in eight of the nine rounds of legislative elections held in post-communist Romania, ranking second in voter preferences only once, in 1996, when it was defeated by a coalition of parties created to remove it from power (the Democratic Convention).

Its percentages ranged from over 66% of the vote in May 1990, the first free elections after the fall of communism (the highest) to only 22% in the 1996 elections (the lowest), remaining at over 35% of voters' preferences in the 2000, 2004 and 2008 elections (alone or in alliance with the small Conservative Party). In the 2012 legislative elections PSD gained the absolute majority of votes, approximately 60%, in alliance with the National Liberal Party, under the logo of the Social-Liberal Union (USL), and in the 2016 elections it got alone over 45%. In the last elections held in December 2020 PSD get the first place with approximately 30% of the votes. The party was the main component of several governing coalitions in the years of post-communism and won the presidential elections three times, in 1990, 1992 and 2000 (by its leader Ion Iliescu).

The National Liberal Party (PNL) is the second largest party, present in eight of the nine post-communist parliaments. Re-established in January 1990 and best placed among the historical parties (those with an interrupted existence during the communist regime), PNL received 7% of the votes in the first elections in May 1990 and misses the entry into parliament in 1992, when it gained only 2.63% from votes. This is the political party that has suffered the most splits since the early 1990s. Its forces increased in the second post-communist decade, following the merger in 2014 with the Liberal Democratic Party (detached from The National Salvation Front-FSN in the early 1990s). PNL was/is part of governing coalitions several times (following the 1996, 2004, 2008, 2012, 2020 elections) and won the presidential elections twice, in 2014 and 2019 (by the president Klaus Iohannis, currently in his second term).

The Democratic Union of Hungarians in Romania (UDMR) has passed all nine parliamentary election tests since 1990. As an ethnic party, it enjoys the constant support of the Hungarian community, getting around 6-7% of the votes each time. UDMR ran each time on his own not in an alliance, to become after elections part of the most post-communist governments.

Two new parties, born from dissatisfaction with the way the old political parties have governed the country have appeared in the last years and are part of the current parliament: USR-PLUS and AUR. USR-PLUS is a progressive, liberal and centrist party, formed by merging USR (The Save Romania Union) and PLUS (The Freedom, Unity and Solidarity Party) in 2020, two parties with civic origin that place themselves in opposition to the existing parties. The oldest of them, USR, founded in 2016, won around 9% of the vote in the parliamentary elections of December 2016, becoming the third largest party. In the 2020 legislative elections USR-PLUS ranks third, with almost 16% of the vote. But the big surprise of this last round of elections is the entry into parliament, with over 9% of the votes, of AUR (The Alliance for the Union of Romanians), a far-right nationalist and populist party, established in 2019.

This unexpected emergence could be explained by the pandemic context (the party having an anti-restrictions, anti-mask-wearing, anti-vaccination message to a population not very educated in health issues), by the lower voter turnout in Romania's parliamentary elections since the fall of communism (only 33%), as well as by the distrust of traditional parties. Other two parties that played a role in the Romanian party system over the last decade through their coalition potential did not reach the 5% threshold for entering the parliament in 2020: The Alliance of Liberals and Democrats- ALDE (founded in 2015 and part of the governing coalition between 2016-2019; merged with Pro Romania party in October 2020 to increase its chances in elections and seceded in early 2021 due to internal frictions between their leaders) and the People's Movement Party- PMP (a center-right party, created in 2013 at the initiative of former Romania's president Traian Basescu).

Therefore, the last legislative elections have challenged to some extent the traditional party system by the entry into parliament of new parties that together accumulate over a quarter of the parliamentary seats (27%). Relevant changes have taken place in the last decade also in the financing of political parties, both in terms of rules and the amount of funding.

Regarding the rules, they have become clearer and stricter with time, evolving from general provisions to more specific regulations starting with the second post-communist decade. The first law dedicated exclusively to financing the activity of political parties and electoral campaigns was issued only in 2006⁸ and has been revised by several times so far⁹. Also in the second post-communist decade it was established the Permanent Electoral Authority, as an autonomous institution with competences of integrated management and control of electoral processes and with clarified and increased attributions over time through successive normative acts.¹⁰

In short, the party and campaign finance (PCF) legislation has two components: private and public (state budget subsidies). The private financing consists of party membership fees and donations. The law does not limit the total income achieved by membership fees, but only the amount of contributions paid in a year by a single party member (it cannot exceed 48 minimum salaries per economy; in 2020, this would mean roughly 22,000 Euros maximum). Consistent with a basic tenet of funding transparency, the law requires parties to publish in the Official Gazette the total amount of contributions as well as the names of party members who paid dues whose value exceeds 10 minimum salaries. Donations received by a party are, instead, capped: they may not exceed in a year 0.025 per cent of the country's budget revenues; the total yearly donations made by an individual may not exceed 200 minimum salaries, and those from a corporation 500 minimum salaries. The law prohibits donations made by legal entities that have debts older than 60 days to the state budget (unless they must recover amounts greater than their own debt), as well as accepting donations or free services from public institutions, state companies, corporations or credit institutions with full or majority state capital, from trade unions and religious denominations. Donations from foreign states or organizations, foreign individuals and companies are also prohibited (except those from foreign parties with which the party in question has political cooperation relations). The law also explicitly states that are forbidden "the acceptance in any form, direct or indirect, of material goods or sums of money or the provision of free services made for the obvious purpose of gaining an economic advantage" (Article 6, paragraph 9), as well as the use of financial, human and technical resources of public institutions or state companies to support the activity of political parties or their electoral campaigns (Article 14, paragraph 1). As in the case of membership fees, the parties have the obligation to publish in the Official Gazette the total amount of donations and loans and the full list of donors whose donations exceed 10 minimum salaries.

⁸ Prior to it, the provisions related to funding parties and campaigns were included in the Law on Political Parties No. 27/1996 and in the Laws 68 and 69/1992 for the election of the Parliament Chambers and of the President of Romania.

⁹ The latest amendments to this law entered into force in January 2018 are available here: <https://www.roaep.ro/prezentare/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Legea-nr.-334-2006-actualizata.pdf>

¹⁰ Law no. 208/2015 on the election of the Senate and the Chamber of Deputies, as well as for the organization and functioning of the Permanent Electoral Authority Text in force since March 10, 2018 <https://www.roaep.ro/prezentare/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/LEGE-Nr-208-2015.pdf>

The public financing of the parties consists of annual public subsidies whose value is at least 0.01% and may not exceed 0.04 % of the yearly state budget revenues. In order to strengthen the political participation of women, for parties that promote women on electoral lists, in eligible places, the amount will be increased twice in proportion to the number of seats gained in elections by women candidates (art. 18, paragraph 2). The subsidy from the state budget takes into account two criteria, the number of votes obtained in the parliamentary elections and the number of votes in local elections and it is distributed as such: 75% of this amount to the parties that reached the electoral threshold, proportional to the number of votes received in the legislative elections and the rest of 25% to the parties that won at least 50 mandates of county councilors in the local elections, proportionally to the number of valid votes cast (art. 19, 20). The subsidy from the state budget is paid monthly by the Permanent Electoral Authority in a special account of each political party. The law stipulates the destinations of these amounts, from the maintenance of headquarters and the organization of political activities, to press and propaganda expenses or travel within the country and abroad, the parties deciding the efficiency and opportunity of these expenses.

A special section of the law refers to the funding of election campaigns. The maximum limits imposed on campaign contributions vary depending on the position for which one runs, from 60 minimum salaries for each candidate for the position of deputy or senator to 750 salaries for each candidate for the European Parliament and 20,000 salaries for a candidate for the president of Romania. Contributions for the election campaign shall be transferred to the bank accounts, especially opened for this purpose and they can come from donations received by candidates from individuals,

from their own income or from loans from individuals or contracted with credit institutions. The financing of the election campaign it is forbidden, in any way, directly or indirectly, by public authorities and institutions, state companies or corporations that carry out activities financed from public funds or carried out such activities 12 months prior to the start of the election campaign, by trade unions, religious denominations, associations, foundations, as well as by foreign citizens (except those who come from other Member States of the European Union, if they are residing in Romania and are members of the party to whose campaign they contribute). The campaign expenditure cannot exceed the maximum ceilings of the contributions provided for each type of candidacy; otherwise, the amounts exceeding these ceilings become revenues to the state budget. Expenditure is reimbursed by the Permanent Electoral Authority if the party wins 3% of the votes nationwide or in constituencies where the 3% threshold has been reached.

Newly formed parties and independent candidates do not receive state grants, which are available for parliamentary parties, and are not entitled to reimbursement of election expenses if they do not reach the 3% threshold in the election. This obstruction of non-parliamentary parties' access to public funds validates the theory of party cartelization, developed by Richard Katz and Peter Mair, according to which parties, being themselves responsible for drafting, voting and implementing the legislation in question and the amount distributed, impose rules from which will benefit themselves, using state resources to ensure their survival and to obtain a privileged position in relation to the newly created parties. In this way, the state becomes a structure to support the parties in the legislature and to exclude new competitors (Katz & Mair, 1995). This is also clear from the analysis of the income sources of political parties in recent years.

4. Parties' money from membership fees, donations and public subsidies

A look at the income sources of political parties in the last decade attests the increase of the financing granted by the state starting with 2017 (Table 1). Between 2010 and 2016 we can see an overwhelming share of the amounts coming from other sources than public subsidies which never exceeded 12.3%.

This fact is confirmed by previous research. A study taking into account the revenues collected between 2003-2010 by the main political parties (Social Democratic Party-PSD, National Liberal Party-PNL,

Democratic Liberal Party-PDL and Democratic Union of the Hungarians in Romania-UDMR) from membership fees, donations and public subsidies, notes that despite the significant state support for these parliamentary formations, the amounts paid from the state budget played rather a marginal role, not exceeding 20% of total revenues (Ionascu & Soare, 2012).

A significant change occurred in 2017, when the grant awarded more than doubled the value of the previous year, followed by an impressive increase in the last three years, close to the maximum limit provided by law, of 0.04% of the total state budget revenues. The public subsidies are directed, according to the law, to the parliamentary parties, in relation to their size and only an insignificant part to the non-parliamentary ones.

Source: unsplash.com. Photo by Ibrahim Boran.

Table 1: The revenues of political parties between 2010-2020, in millions of Lei (Romania's currency, 1 Lei= 4.9 Euros)

Year	Public Subsidies	Other Revenues (membership fees, donations)	Total	Public Subsidies (%)	Other Revenues (%)
2010	4.68	39.96	44,64	10,5%	89,5%
2011	3.74	36.87	40,61	9%	91%
2012	6.27	109.27	115,54	5,4%	94,5%
2013	6.13	46.37	52,5	11,6%	88,4%
2014	4.63	56.88	61,51	7,5%	92,5%
2015	5.77	41.25	47,02	12,3%	87,7%
2016	13.48	159.85	173,85%	7,7%	92,3%
2017	30.03	54.36	84,39	35,5%	64,5%
2018	170.34	53.57	223,91	76%	24%
2019	248.37	141.33	389,7	63,7%	36,3%
2020	237.1	339.83	576,93	42%	58%

Data sources: The Permanent Electoral Authority, <https://finantarepartide.ro/> (author's elaboration)

In addition to public subsidies, the party member and the donor are the main contributors to the party budget, and their contribution is important especially in the case of large parties. This is clear from the annual income and expenditure reports that parties are required to publish in the Official Gazette, according to the law.

Cumulating the data of the five years, from 2016 to 2020, available on the Permanent Electoral Authority website (Table 2), even if the information provided by political parties is sometimes incomplete, we can notice that there is more discipline in collecting dues in the election years. If we look for example at the Social Democratic Party (PSD), a party with over half a million members, it collected from membership fees in 2016 election year over 15 million lei (meaning over 3 million Euros), almost double compared to subsequent years, 2017, 2018, when no elections took place. In the 2020 election year, the lesser contributions were offset by generous funding from the state budget.

Table 2: Revenues of the main political parties from Membership Fees (MF) and Donations (D), in millions of Lei (*1 Lei =4.9 Euros), between 2016 and 2020

Party	2016		2017		2018		2019		2020	
	MF	D	MF	D	MF	D	MF	D	MF	D
PSD	15,09	4,09	8,53	0,12	8,5	0,07	10,06	0,04	11,07	0,41
PNL	8,17	21,9	6,65	0,56	6,77	0,23	6,76	7,21	7,42	59,7
USR	0,03	4,02	0,25	0,28	0,9	0,11	2,46	0,41	3,25	0,23
UDMR	0,93	3,42	0,95	0,11	1,41	0,74	1,59	0,36	-	0,63
PMP	0,45	-	0,7	-	0,65	0,025	0,67	0,026	0,9	0,023
ALDE	2,12	0,86	1,45	-	2,69	0,06	4,13	-	1,17	-

Data sources: The Permanent Electoral Authority, <https://finantarepartide.ro/> (author's elaboration)

The National Liberal Party (PNL), the second largest party, has a systematic collection of membership dues during the five years (with a higher percentage in 2016 election year). Among the smaller parties, both the Democratic Union of Hungarians in Romania (UDMR) and the Popular Movement Party (PMP) have improved their collection of membership fees over the five years. Between the newly formed parties, The Alliance of European Liberals and Democrats (ALDE) and The Union Save Romania (USR), both established in 2015, the discrepancies in this income category are obvious. ALDE, based on a pre-existing structure (through the merger of the Conservative Party with the Liberal Reform Party, detached in 2014 from PNL, led by Călin Popescu Țăriceanu) raised more money from contributions than USR, instead USR collects much more consistent income from donations, thus compensating, at least in part, for the lack of solid territorial organizations with contributing members. This trend was reversed in 2020, when ALDE went into decline, failing to enter to the Parliament following the 2020 legislative elections.

The above data allow the examination of donors' contribution to party budgets.

In the case of a large left-wing party as PSD is, donations are rather moderate (with a peak in 2016) and a much more important source of income is the party base, members who regularly pay small dues. To the right of the political spectrum, more precisely for PNL, the donations have an overwhelming weight in the electoral years. PNL has collected from donations, both in 2016 and 2020 electoral years, much more than all the other parties together. The law requires political parties to publish the names of those who donate amounts whose cumulative value exceeds 10 minimum salaries. The information available on the website of the Permanent Electoral Authority show, for example, that in 2016, 374 people have donated 18,497,621 lei (approx. 3.8 million Euros) to PNL.¹¹ Among them are well-known members of the party, such as Emil Boc, Raluca Turcan, Gheorghe Falcă, Cornel Popa and others, who donated amounts that exceed their salaries as civil servants. Although the return of part of the salary is a (almost) common and accepted practice within the political parties in Romania, it raises even more questions when the donors are such generous employees in the public sector.

¹¹ Data available here: <http://www.roaep.ro/finantare/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/Partidul-National-Liberal.pdf>.

The influential party member, often occupying important positions in the public sector, is the main contributor to the party's budget, much more important than external sources of funding. It is a practice that the media has revealed to have taken place in successive electoral campaigns¹², comparing the amounts of money donated to political parties to support the election campaign, published in the Official Gazette, with the assets and interest declarations of public officials. This practice continues in recent years, even if the parties received the most money from the state budget in their history of post-communist public funding.

A monitoring¹³ carried out by the Expert Forum shows, after a thorough analysis of hundreds of assets declarations of people who made donations to political parties in the 2020 election year, that in many cases those people have no income to justify these contributions. The monitoring has identified such situations in the case of donors or people who have borrowed different parties, such as PSD, Pro Romania, AUR or PNL, the donations being in some cases ten times higher than their annual income. This situation should draw more attention to the institutions empowered to verify the income and legality of donor assets. As previous studies on clientelism have suggested, these practices are a way to get into the party's favor when it comes to power and distorts the idea of fair competition within parties by directing funds to "buy" a place on the list or to secure a person's candidacy.

An important issue remains how public money is spent. The next section aims to analyze how responsible political parties are in spending public money and to present some illustrative examples of state embezzlement in the last decade. A good picture of this issue is offered by the official data on the spending of public money by the parties, provided by the Permanent Electoral Authority.

Source: freepik.com. Photo by pressphoto.

¹² A media report about those who donated in 2009 presidential election campaign more money than their income, available here: <https://cursdeguvernare.ro/oamenii-care-dau-la-partid-mai-multi-bani-decat-castiga-finantarea-campaniilor-electorale.html>.

¹³ Financing political parties in 2020: transparency and irregularities, available at: <https://expertforum.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/PB-118-finantarepolitica-27mai2021.pdf>.

5. How do parties spend public money? State embezzlement mechanisms and practices

The Permanent Electoral Authority is the institution in charge of verifying the legality of the expenses made by political parties, both from the state budget subsidies and from private funds.

An analysis of the annual reports of this institution¹⁴ attests numerous deviations from the provisions of the law, both regarding party revenues (exceeding legal ceilings, electoral contributions from other sources other than those permitted by law etc.), as well as the use of money (exceeding the percentages by types of expenses, payments of other expenses than those permitted by law, expenses higher than the contributions, incomplete supporting documents etc.).

One of the most notorious cases of embezzlement of public money in recent years through the illegal use of the subsidy from the state budget had in the foreground the former treasurer and former PSD deputy, Mircea Drăghici. He was sentenced in the summer of 2021 to five years in prison for embezzling money from PSD subsidies. Involved with the management and administration of assets and funds belonging to PSD, he used in 2018 the amount of 380.000 euros from the subsidy granted to the party by the Permanent Electoral Authority to

buy a house for himself. With this money, Drăghici partially covered (more than 2/3) the value of the respective building.

The purchase was disguised as a lease agreement which stated that the money would be paid by the party as rent, and not for the benefit of its treasurer.¹⁵ He became the first person from the party's leadership who has been convicted of illegal use of subsidies allocated to political parties.

Other cases of irresponsible spending of public money consist of unjustified and exaggerated purchases, such as luxury cars, totally contrary to the spirit of the law, the purpose of the subsidies being to support the proper functioning and political activity of parties. Thus, the acquisition of luxury cars, Tesla and Mercedes, by the Pro Romania party, led by former Prime Minister Victor Ponta, is emblematic in this respect. The party received a substantial subsidy from the state budget in 2020 (over 2.5 million euros), although it was not entitled to receive it because it did not run in the 2016 elections. In order to support the liberal government by voting the state budget law in the Parliament, an exception was made to the party funding law. More specifically, the Parliament passed an amendment initiated by the Pro Romania party, in which it was stipulated that parties that did not participate in the elections, such as Pro-Romania, but which in the meantime were formed in the Parliament, by the migration of parliamentarians from other parties, will also be entitled to receive the subsidy.¹⁶

¹⁴ Available here: <https://finantarepartide.ro/raport-anual-dcfppce/>.

¹⁵ <https://www.agerpres.ro/justitie/2021/07/01/fostul-trezorier-al-psd-mircea-draghici-condamnat-definitiv-la-5-ani-inchisoare-pentru-delapidare--740985>

¹⁶ <https://romania.europalibera.org/a/30367756.html>

The party directed the largest percentage of the money received from the state in investments, although it remained with significant debts following the 2020 parliamentary election (when the party failed to meet the threshold for the Parliament, and the Permanent Electoral Authority decided to not reimburse the full amount spent on the election campaign). However, they manage to buy three luxury cars in one year, which cost between 300,000-350,000 euros.¹⁷

More recent data published by the Permanent Electoral Authority¹⁸ refer to the expenses made by the political parties between January-September 2021 (see the figure below). According to these data, the parties in Romania received from the state budget, in the first nine months of 2021, 118 million lei (approx. 24 million euros) considering their results in the parliamentary and local elections (in proportion of 75% and 25% respectively). Most of the subsidies went to the first two largest parties, PSD (approx. 9.2 million euros) and PNL (approx. 7.8 million euros).

Figure 1: Political parties expenditures from the state budget subsidies, January-September 2021

Data sources: The Permanent Electoral Authority report¹⁹ and The Expert Forum monitoring report²⁰ (author's elaboration)

The data published by the Permanent Electoral Authority shows that the parties managed to spend only about half of the allocated amount. The newly formed party AUR had an atypical behavior in this regard; it did not spend any money of the more than 1.8 million euros received. The party's leaders announced that they would initiate a bill to stop party funding, considered a "robbery of public money," and would use the money they have already received to build a hospital.²¹ This is the kind of message to which at least part of the public is increasingly receptive, in a general context of rising prices and declining real incomes, the generous sums allocated to political parties being perceived as a defiance to citizens.

¹⁷ <https://romania.europalibera.org/a/exclusiv-creditorii-execute-bolidul-ponta-tesla-x-133-000-euro-560-cai/31333804.html>.

¹⁸ Available here: <https://finantarepartide.ro/> (accessed on March 13th 2022).

¹⁹ Permanent Electoral Authority, Statement of expenditure incurred from the state budget subsidy in January-September 2021, available at: <https://finantarepartide.ro/>

²⁰ Expert Forum, The secrets of political subsidies, available at: <https://expertforum.ro/secretele-subventiilor-politice/>

²¹ <https://newsweek.ro/politica/video-liderul-aur-sustine-ca-nu-vrea-subventia-pentru-partide-cu-banii-facem-un-spital>

This is the reason why several civic associations have called for an end to excessive allocations of funds to parties, which in many cases do not have the capacity to spend it or make completely unjustified expenditures and to put a stop to arbitrary practices of allocating funds (such as the one mentioned above in the case of Pro Romania party).²²

Examining the categories of expenses incurred by the parties (Figure 1), it is noticeable that more than half of the money spent is on press and propaganda. Both main parties, PSD and PNL, used more than half of their money for “press and propaganda” expenses (PSD over 66% of the subsidy received and PNL -58% of the subsidy). Therefore, the main parties tend to turn subsidies into a mechanism for financing the press and building the image. This ultimately raises serious questions about the editorial independence of the press, which are being paid millions of euros from party subsidies. This way, the citizens’ rights to correct information is limited by the very political parties that they finance.

These examples of the abusive and extravagant use of subsidies received from the state budget are accompanied by other indirect practices of embezzling public money. They are numerous and cross-party; this study uses a few cases from the last decade, illustrative for deciphering some mechanisms of embezzlement of the state. The most widespread forms of using public money indirectly, violating the legal provisions, are the misuse of material and human resources of public institutions for political and electoral purposes; discretionary allocation of public money by the ruling party; illegal financing of parties and electoral campaigns for subsequent illegitimate benefits etc.

Although the law prohibits the use of financial, human and technical resources of public institutions to support the activities of political parties and their electoral campaigns, there have been numerous cases reported by the media in which the means from the endowment of institutions which local elected officials, parliamentarians or ministers represented, were used for electoral purposes or for the interest of their party. A well-known public inquiry in recent years regarding the use of human resources of public institutions for the benefit of its own party had in the foreground the Social Democratic Party (PSD) leader Liviu Dragnea.²³ In his former position as president of the Teleorman County Council, Dragnea intervened to keep in office and pay the salaries of two employees of the General Directorate of Social Assistance and Child Protection (DGASPC) Teleorman, although he knew that they were not at work and they did not perform any of the activities included in their employment contract, they were actually working for the PSD Teleorman organization. This case of fictitious employment, in which Liviu Dragnea was accused of the abusive use of his position of power, ultimately leading to his conviction, draws attention to a phenomenon, that of the abusive use of political power by the so-called “local barons”, for which the city or the county they lead becomes a feud.

Even if the legislation has become clearer and harsher in punishing those who break the law, the political parties have also perfected the methods and tools by which they disregard it. From the “innocent” (and less expensive) practices of electoral bribery (sausages, beer, food packages, buckets, scarves or hats), they moved to “disguised” practices, which take the form of public contracts, at overvalued prices, implemented by approved companies, part of the money returning to the parties for illegal financing of electoral campaigns or in the pockets of politicians.

²² <https://expertforum.ro/opriti-alocarile-arbitrare-subventii-partide/>

²³ <https://www.mediafax.ro/politic/liviu-dragnea-a-fost-condamnat-la-inchisoare-cu-executare-sentinta-definitiva-in-dosarul-angajarilor-fictive-18145262>

One of the most telling cases is that of the businessman Ioan Niculae, convicted in 2015 for illegally funding Mircea Geoana's presidential campaign with one million euros in 2009.²⁴ According to anti-corruption prosecutors, to disguise the money's destination, different amounts were used to pay various service providers for the electoral campaign, including institutions involved in conducting public opinion polls. In exchange for the money offered, Ioan Niculae would have requested that, if Mircea Geoana had won the elections, to appoint people to support his interests within the Ministry of Economy and Trade and within state-owned companies (Transgaz and Romgaz) to get preferential prices for gas.

It is not the purpose of this paper to enumerate too many cases of corruption, they are multiple and cross-party, but these few examples are illustrative for understanding the mechanisms of state embezzlement, far from exhausting them. Think-tanks specialized in public policies and the promotion of good governance constantly monitored the management of public funds, finding numerous irregularities.²⁵ Manipulating public procurement procedures and embezzlement of the state-owned companies are frequently used by those in positions of power for their own enrichment and fundraising for the party. The widespread practices are the payment of commissions by businessmen (usually 10-20% of the contracts' value) to the president of the county council, mayor, director, minister, etc., in order to win a public procurement (such as a road maintenance) or the request for bribes by decision makers for the approval of payments for works already executed by companies (one of these examples is the "Gala Bute" corruption case, in which the former Minister Elena Udrea was convicted for coordinating a system through which her relatives received money from several companies to guarantee the timely payment of works financed by the Ministry of Regional Development and Tourism, led by her at that time. Part of the sums would have reached the Bucharest branch of the Democratic-Liberal Party, being used also to finance campaigns to defame opponents or journalists).

Source: freepik.com.
Photo by freepik.

²² <http://www.mediafax.ro/politic/dosarul-mita-la-psd-trei-ani-si-doi-ani-si-sase-luni-de-inchisoare-cu-executare-pentru-buniasi-niculae-instanta-a-mai-decis-confiscarea-sumei-de-641-000-de-lei-de-la-ioan-niculae-14104291>

²³ See, for example, The Romanian Academic Society, "Misuse of Public Funds in Romania Before and After EU Accession", available at <http://sar.org.ro/initiativa-fonduri-europene-manual-de-fraudare/?lang=en> and The Expert Forum, "Money and politics. The links between public procurement and political parties", available at: http://expertforum.ro/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/PB-61_ro.pdf.

6. Discussions and conclusions

This brief review shows that the illicit financing strategies of parties and politicians are diverse, constantly changing and adapting to legislative changes.

Overvalued contracts (including consultancy contracts and feasibility studies), fictitious services, appointing people close to the ruling party/parties to key positions in state-owned companies to facilitate the preferential award of public money contracts, abusive allocations of funds to party clients are the preferred ways of embezzling the state.

The contracts financed by the state budget present a higher corruption risks than those receiving European funding (Mungiu Pippidi et al., 2015) due to lower managerial control and performance, although fraud and clientelism are not lacking in European funding either.

Thus, strengthening the administrative capacity of the state, including through a coherent legal framework (frequent changes in public procurement law, over-legislation are examples of bad practice) and through the transparent and correct use of information systems (e-government works well in conditions of honesty, responsibility and competence of the public administration), doubled by the firm punishment of those guilty of breaking the law could reduce the scourge of corruption.

And, because anti-corruption efforts are most often a matter of collective action (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2017), they must also aim at developing the capacity of the electorate to sanction the corrupt practices of the parties, this sanction not being translated into absenteeism at the polls, but in the increase of intolerance towards favoritism and corruption. As the paper has shown, the state has become increasingly generous in financing political parties, the amounts allocated to them from the public budget increasing considerably in recent years. This growth should in principle diminish their dependence on financial interest groups and corrupt practices. Funding regulations and control levers were also improved during the years, including by establishing an agency (Permanent Electoral Authority) with a clear mandate and powers.

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The relevant contribution that this paper makes to the studies on party finance consists in showing that a more generous financing of political parties does not automatically entail a greater integrity of their behavior and practices.

In some cases, subsidies have become a tool for irresponsible spending, but also for promotion and purchase media services. Additional mechanisms should be developed to monitor the spending of funds allocated to parties, to periodically determine their impact and, where appropriate, to change the amount of funding. Instead of giving parliamentary parties money exceeding their needs, it would be better to provide more financial support to small parties that have not passed the threshold. It is desirable both to limit the public funding of parliamentary parties to a reasonable level, according to objective and fair criteria, without exceptions and derogations that change the funding rules to the liking of the parliamentary majority of the time, and to extend it to small parties and new parties in order to increase their chances of competing in elections.

Change should also come from political parties, because laws, no matter how harsh, will probably never be able to cover up all the maneuvers invented to ignore them. If the parties do not understand that the votes received in the elections (at a level of electoral participation that places them at the limit of political legitimacy) do not give them the right to clientelize the administration and to abuse public resources, the rift between them and society will deepen even more, and the chances of becoming respectable organizations will decrease accordingly.

Source: freepik.com.
Photo by freepik.

References

- Casal Bertoa, F. and Spirova, M. (2019), "Parties between thresholds: Public subsidies and party behaviour in post-communist democracies", *Party Politics*, Vol. 25(2) 233–244.
- Casal Bertoa, F. and Van Biezen, I. (2014), "Party regulation and party politics in post-communist Europe", *East European Politics*, 30:3, 295–314.
- Diamond, L. and Gunther, R. (eds.), (2001), *Political Parties and Democracy*, Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Dimulescu, V., Pop R., Doroftei M., (2013), "Bottom of the Heap. The Case of Romania", in Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (ed.), *Controlling Corruption in Europe, The Anticorruption Report*, Volume 1, Barbara Budrich Publishers, pp. 83–98.
- Gherghina, S., Chiru, M., Casal Bertoa, F., (2011), "State resources and pocket money: The financing of the Romanian political parties in post-communism", in Gherghina, S. (ed.), *Votes and politics. The dynamics of the Romanian parties in the last two decades*, (in Romanian), Iasi: European Institute, pp. 235–257.
- Gherghina, S. and Chiru, M., (2013), "Taking the Short Route Political Parties, Funding Regulations, and State Resources in Romania", *East European Politics & Societies*, 27(1): 108–128.
- Gherghina, S. and Volintiru, C., (2021), "Political parties and clientelism in transition countries: evidence from Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine", *Acta Politica*, 56: 677–693.
- Gherghina, S. and Volintiru, C., (2017), "A new model of clientelism: political parties, public resources, and private contributors", *European Political Science Review*, 9(1), Cambridge University Press: 115–137.
- Grzymała-Busse, A., (2007), *Rebuilding Leviathan: Party Competition and State Exploitation in Post-Communist Democracies*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ionașcu A. and Soare S., (2012), "Looking for a Mecenaz. Mechanisms and processes of financing political parties in post-communist Romania", *The Sphere of Politics* (in Romanian), Nr. 169/2012, p. 56–65.
- Ionita, S., Nutu, O., Stefan, L., and Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2011), "Beyond perception. Has Romania's governance improved after 2004?", *Romanian Journal of Political Science*, 11(1), 8–28.
- Katz, R. S. and Mair, P. (1995), "Changing Models of Party Organization and Party Democracy: The Emergence of the Cartel Party", *Party Politics*, No 1/1995.

- Katz, R. S. and Mair, P. (2009)**, “The Cartel Party Thesis: A Restatement”, *Perspectives on Politics*, Vol. 7, No. 4, p. 753-766.
- Kopecky, P. and Van Biezen, I. (2007)**, “The State and the Parties: Public Funding, Public Regulation and Rent-Seeking in Contemporary Democracies”, *Party Politics*, vol. 13, n. 2, pp. 235-254.
- Koß, M. (2010)**, *The politics of party funding*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2010.
- Kopecky, P. (ed), (2008)**, *Political Parties and State in Post-Communist Europe*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Kopecky, P. and Spirova, M. (2011)**, “Jobs for the Boys’? Patterns of Party Patronage in Post-Communist Europe”, *West European Politics*, 34(5):897-921.
- Kopecký, P., Mair, P. and Spirova, M. (2012)**, *Party Patronage and Party Government in European Democracies*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Mair, P. (1997)**, “What is Different about Post-Communist Systems?“, in *Party System Change. Approaches and Interpretations*, Oxford: Clarendon Press, p. 175-199.
- Mateescu, S.-D. (2011)**, “The impact of the of the party system cartelization in Romania on the democratic system”, *The Sphere of Politics (in Romanian)*, Nr. 162/2011, p. 12-23.
- Matiuta, C. (2018)**, *Who I’m voting for? Dynamics of the party system in Romania: 1990-2018 (in Romanian)*, Iasi: European Institute.
- Mungiu-Pippidi, A. and Fazekas, M. (2020)**, “How to define and measure corruption”, in Mungiu-Pippidi, A. and Heywood, P. M. (eds.), *A research agenda for studies of corruption*, Edward Elgar Publishing, Chapter 2, pp. 7-27.
- Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2017)**, *In search of good governance. How have other countries escaped corruption? (in Romanian)*, Iași: Polirom.
- Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (ed.), (2015)**, *Government Favouritism in Europe. The Anticorruption Report, Volume 3*, Barbara Budrich Publishers.
- Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (ed.), (2013)**, *Controlling Corruption in Europe, The Anticorruption Report, Volume 1*, Barbara Budrich Publishers.
- Mungiu-Pippidi, A. (2010)**, *A Case Study in Political Clientelism. Romania’s Policy-Making Mayhem*, available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1686617.
- Popescu, M. and Soare, S. (2014)**, “Engineering party competition in a new democracy: postcommunist party regulation in Romania”, *East European Politics*, 30(3): 389–411.

- Protsyk, O. and Matichescu M.L. (2011)**, “Clientelism and Political Recruitment in Democratic Transition: Evidence from Romania”, *Comparative Politics*, 43(2).
- Roper, S. (2006)**, “The influence of party patronage and state finance on electoral outcomes: Evidence from Romania”, *Journal of Communist Studies and Transition Politics* 22(3): 362–382.
- Roper, S. (2007)**, “The differential impact of state finance on the Romanian party system”, *Europe-Asia Studies*, 59(1): 97–109.
- Roper, S., Moraru, A. and Iorga, E. (2008)**, “Romania: The Secondary Influence of Public Finance on the Party System”, in Roper, S. and Ikstens. J. (eds), *Public Finance and Post Communist Party Development*, Ashgate Publishing, Ltd., pp. 143–154.
- Roper, S. and Ikstens, J. (eds.), (2008)**, *Public Finance and Post-Communist Party Development*, Aldershot: Ashgate.
- Rose, R. and Mishler, W. (1998)**, “Negative and Positive Party Identification in Post-Communist Countries”, *Electoral Studies*, 17(2): 217–34
- Smilov, D. and Toplak, J. (eds), (2017)**, *Political Finance and Corruption in Eastern Europe: The Transition Period*. Aldershot: Ashgate Publishing Limited.
- Van Biezen, I. (2010)**, “Campaign and party finance”, in Lawrence, L. D., Richard, G. N. and Norris. P. (eds.), *Comparing democracies: Elections and Voting in Global Perspective*, London: Sage.
- Van Biezen, I. (2004)**, “Political Parties as Public Utilities”, *Party Politics*, Vol. 10 (6), pp. 701–722.
- Van Biezen, I. (2003)**, *Political Parties in New Democracies: Party Organization in Southern and East-Central Europe*, London: Palgrave.
- Van Biezen I., Mair P. and Poguntke T. (2012)**, “Going, going... gone? The Decline of Party Membership in Contemporary Europe”, *European Journal of Political Research*, Vol. 51(1), pp. 24–56.
- Van Biezen I. and Poguntke T. (2014)**, “The decline of membership-based politics”, *Party Politics*, Vol. 20(2), pp. 205–216.
- Van Biezen, I. (2000)**, “On the Internal Balance of Party Power: Party Organizations in New Democracies”, *Party Politics*, 6: 395–417.
- Volintiru, C. (2015)**, “The exploitative function of party patronage: does it serve the party’s interest?”, *East European Politics* 31(1), Routledge: 39–55.
- Walecki, M., (2003)**, „Money and Politics in Central and Eastern Europe”, *Funding of Political Parties and Election Campaign*, IDEA Handbook Series.

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